

**Effects of Performance-Based Financial Incentives on Work Performance: A Study of
Technical-Level Employees in Private Sector in Sri Lanka**

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Abstract

The objective of the study is to investigate the effect of performance-based financial incentives on work performance. The study hypothesized that the design features of performance-based financial incentive schemes themselves may influence individuals' work performance. For the study, survey methodology was used and 93 technical-level employees who were subjected to a performance-based incentive scheme for at least two years in their firms responded. Regression analysis was used for data analysis. It was found that the design features of performance-based financial incentives schemes explain 51 per cent of the variance in work performance. Six of the incentive scheme factors, including the goals of incentive scheme, employee participation in setting goals, incentive scheme type, and payout frequency have significant positive impact on work performance. Overall, the findings suggest that well-designed and carefully implemented incentive schemes have significant positive impact on work performance.

Keywords: financial incentives, performance-based financial incentives, Sri Lanka, work performance.

Organizations offer attractive financial incentive packages to attract and retain people with high quality and thereby to stay competitive (Hutson, 2000; Lawton & Chernyshenko, 2008). The literature also suggests the possibility of maintaining more than one incentive package within a single organization in order to meet needs and desires of different employee groups (Lawler, 1990). This paper presents results of a study that investigated the effect of design features of performance-based financial incentives on work performance of technical-level employees attached full-time to diverse organizations belong to the private service sector in Sri Lanka.

Although it is expected that financial incentives increase individual effort and thereby produce "incentivized" behaviour, previous research conducted in both controlled laboratory studies and field studies provide inconclusive results. For instance, some studies provide evidence that financial incentives increase individual effort and thereby produce incentivized behaviour (Bonner & Sprinkle, 2002; Stone, Bryant, & Wier, 2010) while some other studies provide evidence that financial incentives fail to produce desired behaviour (Wolf & Zwick,

2008) and create negative organizational outcomes such as decreased trust and cooperation (Stone et al., 2010). The current study attempted to explain whether performance-based financial incentives could make an influence on work performance of technical-level employees. In this regard, the literature makes a distinction between “mental” work tasks (cognitive tasks) and “physical” work tasks (manual labour) (Condly, Clark, & Stolovitch, 2003). Condly et al. (2003) investigated the effect of incentives on cognitive and manual labour and found that somewhat greater performance gains were realized for manual work than for cognitive work. However, we have not come across empirical studies that investigated influence of performance-based financial incentives on work performance of technical-level employees. Further, as little research has been directed to investigate performance-based financial incentives, for this study we have drawn literature from financial incentives (such as Jenkins et al., 1998; Rose & Manley, 2010) as well as incentives in general (such as Stolovitch, Clark, & Condly, 2002). Therefore, in this article, the terms such as performance-based financial incentives, financial incentives, and incentives are used interchangeably.

In investigating the effect of design features of performance-based financial incentives on work performance the study hypothesized that the design features of performance-based financial incentive schemes themselves may influence individuals’ work performance. By doing so, the study makes a contribution to the literature in several ways. First, the literature suggests that the failures of even well-designed incentive schemes raise the question as to why organizations introduce such schemes (Marsden, 2003). This suggests the need of more empirical studies in this area. Second, the review of literature suggests that the majority of articles in academic publications in the area of performance-based financial incentives and work performance are practitioner viewpoints (e.g. Hutson, 2000) or conceptual papers (e.g. Hoffman & Rogelberg, 1998). Further, some studies were typical laboratory experiments where participants know they are in an experiment while some other studies were laboratory simulations where an attempt is made to make the

experiment as realistic and authentic as possible (Condly et al., 2003). In this regard, Condly et al. (2003) state that field studies conducted in real work settings are more generalizable than other types of studies. Third, although a few empirical research studies have been conducted on incentives (e.g. Rose & Manley, 2010; Stolovitch et al, 2002; Wolf & Zwick, 2008) such empirical research attempts have not taken off worldwide. Fourth, in such circumstances, organizations tend to implement incentive systems without a clear understanding of the factors that increase the positive effects and eliminate negative consequences (Stolovitch et al, 2002). This situation highlights the need of more empirical studies to produce new insights beyond prior studies to the literature within an extended framework. As performance-based financial incentives present an exciting area of research we believe that the findings of the current study would be of interest to academics and practitioners worldwide. It is expected that the findings of the study will provide academics and practitioners with new insights into design features of financial incentive schemes that influence work performance. Further, it is expected that the findings of the study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

The article is in four sections. The first section reviews the relevant literature. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. In the final section, conclusions on the findings are drawn, implications of the findings are discussed, and research areas for further inquiry and understanding are presented.

Theoretical Background and Hypothesis

Financial Incentives

The literature suggests that the design features of financial incentives have a strong motivational effect on employees if they value it, if they believe good performance is instrumental in bringing the desired reward and if they expect their efforts will achieve the desired performance (Lawler, 1971). Further, according to the literature, any incentive

system may fail if employees feel they lack scope to increase their effort, if they feel their effort make little difference to their performance, and if they believe that management lacks the competence or the good faith to evaluate and reward their performance fairly (Marsden, 2003). In such circumstances, employees may view incentive schemes as unfair and divisive (Marsden, 2003). Furthermore, Still and Cundiff (1969, p. 268) state that incentive schemes should be able to fulfil at least three major functions, namely, remunerating the individual for his/her work, motivating the individual to devote the largest possible amount of effort to his/her task in terms of quantity and quality, and channelling individuals' effort toward various activities according to the objectives and priorities of the firm.

According to Stolovitch et al (2002), incentive systems work best when current performance is inadequate, desired performance can be quantified (in terms of how much, how often, and how many) and when goals are challenging but achievable. In this regard, Condly et al. (2003) argue that employees wish to increase quantity of performance, quality of performance or occasionally both quantity and quality of performance in respect to incentives. Further, Rose and Manley (2010) suggest that financial incentives should have multiple goals covering different project areas and flexibility to modify goals and measurement procedures over time. They further state the importance of employees having a clear understanding of how financial incentives align with overall objectives of the work. Therefore, Marsden (2003) states that goal setting and appraisal play a critical role between the incentive system and employee effort. Further, Rose and Manley (2010) emphasize the importance of employee participation in designing the financial incentive system.

The literature distinguishes between two types of incentive programmes, namely individual-based incentive programmes and team-based incentive programmes (Condly et al., 2003; Hoffman & Rogelberg, 1998). According to Condly et al. (2003), individuals have more control over an outcome when it is more or less under the individual control. However, according to Condly et al. (2003), in team-based incentive programmes, an individual may in fact put in considerable effort as a member of a team, yet may not realize any incentive

because of performance lapses on the part of team members. In this regard, Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) argue that the effectiveness of a team-based incentive system depends on team interdependence (both within and between teams) and team type (i.e., full or part-time).

Condly et al. (2003) distinguish incentive schemes between competitive programmes and non-competitive programmes. In competitive programs, only the highest performers get incentives while in non-competitive programmes everyone participating in the incentive programme can potentially earn incentives if they meet or exceed preset performance goals (Condly et al., 2003). In this regard, Condly et al. (2003) argue that competitive incentive programmes might be less effective than those where everyone who increases their performance to agreed levels is eligible to receive an incentive.

According to the literature, incentive term is also an important feature of incentive schemes, where some incentive programmes last only a few days or weeks while others go on for years (Condly et al., 2003). Hence, Condly et al. (2003) have categorized incentives schemes based on the incentive term as long-term (6 months or longer), intermediate-term (1 month to 6 months), and short-term (less than one month). Further, Condly et al. (2003) argue that the term of an incentive programme might influence employees' effort and they suggested that short-term programmes might be more effective than otherwise.

Effect of Incentives on Work Performance

Work performance implicitly means doing better or worse than comparable other (Price, 1997). The majority of previous research relied on self-report measures of individual performance because the individual is uniquely aware of the elements of high performance when the focus is on the perspective of the individual employee (Rodwell, Kienzle, & Shadur, 1998). Marsden (2003) states that organizations have to rely on incentives to get better work performance from employees as direct supervision is problematic or expensive in many work contexts.

However, according to Stolovitch et al. (2002) controversy and uncertainty have characterized the issue of using incentives to improve work performance. On the one hand, some scholars argue that incentives should not be given for performance that would normally be achieved without them (Eisenberger, Rhoades, & Cameron, 1999) and some others argue that incentives destroy personal interest in work (Deci, 1971 and 1972). Further, although Wolf and Zwick (2008) expected to find that financial incentives increase establishment productivity they did not find any support for their contention.

On the other hand, several other scholars argue that well-designed and carefully implemented incentive schemes have dramatic positive impact on work performance (Condly et al., 2003; Rose & Manley, 2010) and on goal achievement (Stolovitch et al, 2002). Yet, the literature suggests that different types of incentives, namely monetary and non-monetary might have different levels of impact on individual performance (Condly et al., 2003). After a meta-analytic review of 45 field and laboratory research on the use of incentives to motivate performance, Condly et al. (2003) identified that although incentives, in general, increase performance monetary incentives result in higher performance gains than non-monetary incentives. However, Pink's (2009) best seller on motivation refutes this. Therefore, more research is needed to empirically investigate the effects of financial incentives on individuals.

In the context of financial incentives, Sliwka (2003) and Rose and Manley (2010) argue that financial incentives can increase the effort of employees towards voluntary performance goals beyond minimum specifications. Further, Stolovitch et al. (2002) found that incentives increase the value people assign to work goals and rewarding employees for exceeding targets causes them to value work more. They further found that incentives heighten self-confidence and employee loyalty. Furthermore, Stolovitch et al. (2002) compared the effectiveness of incentive systems on quality versus quantity of outputs. However, they had not found any significant differences in quality or quantity of outputs based on incentives. Therefore, they concluded that incentive systems affect quality and

quantity equally and positively. In addition, another important aspect of financial incentives is the ideal amount of financial incentives. However, our literature review failed to find previous studies that investigated how the amount of financial incentives influence work performance. Therefore, we have attempted to address this aspect to some extent by incorporating it as a sub-variable of the main variable “incentive scheme’s reward base” of our study.

Some previous studies have compared the influence of individual-based and team-based incentives on employee work performance (Condly et al., 2003; Stolovitch et al., 2002). For instance, Condly et al. (2003) and Stolovitch et al. (2002) found that team-based incentives had a markedly superior effect on performance compared to individual-based incentives.

Consistent with the majority of the findings of the previous research that indicate incentives increase work performance, it is proposed for the current study that the design features of performance-based financial incentives increase work performance. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis: Design features of performance-based financial incentives have significant positive effect on work performance.

Figure 1 shows the hypothesised research model.

Take in Figure 1

Methodology

Sample

The employment structure in Sri Lanka is classified into seven major occupational groups, namely, Managerial/professional and technical, Clerical/secretarial, Craft and related occupations, Sales and personal services, Skilled agricultural and fishery workers, Machine operators (Manufacturing), and Elementary occupations (Ministry of Education, 2007). The study was confined to technical-level employees. Job responsibilities of technical level

employees include but not limited to the application of scientific knowledge in designing and developing products and processes, and engineering plants and equipment; planning and designing engineering work in manufacturing industries, electrical power systems, hydraulic structures, buildings, roads, highways and bridges, railways, and public health systems; overall execution of engineering projects and management. The target population for the study is a broad cross-section of full-time technical-level employees in the private sector firms located in Colombo, which is considered as the main commercial and financial hub of Sri Lanka. The three available directories, i.e., Colombo Stock Exchange, the Registrar of Companies, and business section of the Sri Lanka Telecom Telephone Directory were used to identify possible firms. With the help of the directories, a random sample of organizations was selected. To distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire across selected organizations, contact persons were identified through commercial and financial associations, employees' welfare associations or trade unions, educational programmes offered for white-collar employees by educational institutes, and personal networks. Contact persons were instructed to identify individuals who were subjected to a performance-based incentive scheme for at least two years in their firms. The one of the authors of this paper together with contact persons distributed the survey questionnaire among a heterogeneous sample of technical-level employees full-time employed and ranked at different levels within the organizations. Participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution, and their responses were anonymous. Of the 120 self-administered questionnaires sent out, 93 completed questionnaires returned within 4 weeks of initial distribution. This yielded a response rate of 78%. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table I.

Take in Table 1

Measures

Work performance was measured by the three items from Bauer and Mulder (2006). Items were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where Cronbach's alpha = 0.772.

Incentive scheme's reward base was measured by six items. Respondent rated each of the six items on a scale of yes or no. The six items were "Incentive scheme's reward base is meeting or exceeding performance goals", "Incentive scheme's reward base is increasing rate of performance", "Incentive scheme's reward base is individuals or teams compete with each other", "Incentive scheme's reward base is achieving or surpassing a score", "Incentive scheme's reward base is profit sharing", and "Incentive scheme's reward base is a percentage of monthly salary".

Incentive scheme type was measured in terms of individual-based, team-based or a combination of individual-based and team-based. Respondent identified whether his/her incentive scheme was belong to any of these three types. Payout frequency inquired the time period of paying out incentives, e.g. in every three months time.

A question was developed to inquire employees' participation in setting goals for the incentive scheme. This item was measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Another question was developed to inquire whether the goals of incentive scheme had been integrated with department/unit goals of the organization. This item was measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Five items were developed to measure the nature of goals of incentive schemes. This item was measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where Cronbach's alpha = 0.701.

Method of Data Collection and Analysis

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. It was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector, 1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs and for deriving hypotheses. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003). For the data analysis, descriptive statistics and multiple regression were used.

Results

The features of the incentive schemes that respondents enjoyed are shown in Table 2. As mentioned in the section on *measures* features are presented under three subheadings, namely, incentive scheme's reward base, incentive scheme type, and payout frequency.

Take in Table 2

The result relating to employee participation in goal setting of the incentive scheme is shown in Table 3. It also shows the result relating to the degree of integration between the goals of incentive scheme and the goals of department/unit from the perspective of the respondents.

Take in Table 3

Results relating to the nature of goals of incentive schemes are shown in Table 4.

Take in Table 4

To investigate the effects of incentive schemes on work performance multiple regression analysis was used. The results are shown in Table 5. The model explains 51 per cent of the variance in work performance ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.509, p < 0.001$). Six of the incentive scheme factors have significant positive impact on work performance. The nature of goals of the incentive scheme have the greatest impact ($\beta = 0.893, p < 0.001$). Incentive scheme's reward base in terms of achieving or surpassing a score ($\beta = 0.855, p < 0.001$) and a percentage of monthly salary ($\beta = 0.571, p < 0.05$) rated at second and third place in terms of the influence on work performance. Incentive scheme type also had significant positive effect on work performance ($\beta = 0.527, p < 0.05$). Further analysis was conducted to identify which incentive scheme type has had the greatest impact. It was found that the combination of individual-based and team-based incentive scheme had the greatest impact followed by team-based incentive scheme (results are not shown in a table). Results also reveal that payout frequency ($\beta = 0.381$) and employee participation in setting goals ($\beta = 0.431$) also have significant positive effects at $p < 0.10$ level.

Take in Table 5

Conclusions and Implications

The main intention of the study was to investigate the effects of design features of performance-based financial incentives on work performance. For the study, a random sample of technical-level employees engaged full time in diverse organisations belong to the service sector in Sri Lanka responded. Drawing from past research, the design features of performance-based financial incentive schemes were measured by incentive scheme's reward base, incentive scheme type, employee participation in setting goals, integration with department/unit goals, and the nature of goals of incentive scheme.

It was found that most common incentive scheme's reward base is meeting or exceeding performance goals, followed by profit sharing basis (refer to Table 2). A percentage of monthly salary and increasing rate of performance were also used as incentive scheme's reward base by the firms. Further, the majority of the respondents experienced individual-based incentive schemes followed by team-based schemes. However, a considerable number had experienced a combination of individual-based and team-based incentive schemes. In this regard, although previous studies (such as Condly et al., 2003; Hoffman & Rogelberg, 1998) suggest the availability of individual-based or team-based incentive schemes we have not come a cross previous studies that investigated a combination of individual-based and team-based incentive schemes. Furthermore, the majority received incentives on annual-basis followed by monthly-basis.

With regard to the employee participation in setting goals for incentives, a mean value of 2.93 does not suggest a high level of employee participation (refer to Table 3). Further, a mean value of 3.27 suggests a moderate level of integration between incentive scheme and department/unit goals. In this regard, past studies such as Rose and Manley (2010) emphasized the importance of employee participation in designing a financial incentive system.

With regard to the nature of goals of incentive scheme, all the five areas investigated are important for effective goal setting of incentive schemes (refer to Table 4). That is, the results suggest that goals set by the scheme should be clear and specific, challenging but achievable, relevant to the job profile, should accurately measure the effort in achieving work goals, and time period given to achieve the work goals should be fair. Past studies such as Marsden (2003) and Rose and Manley (2010) also highlighted the need of effective goal setting in providing incentives for employees.

The main objective of the study was to identify the design features of performance-based financial incentives that impact on work performance. The results of the multiple regression analysis revealed that six design features, namely, the nature of goals of incentive scheme, incentive scheme's reward base of achieving or surpassing a score and a percentage of monthly salary, incentive scheme type of a combination of individual-based and team-based, employee participation in setting goals, and payout frequency have positive and significant effect of work performance (refer to Table 5). However, the level of integration between incentive scheme and department/unit goals did not show significant impact on work performance. The findings support the claims made by previous studies such as Stolovitch et al. (2002) and Condly et al. (2003) that well-designed and carefully implemented incentive systems increase work performance.

However, it should be noted that surprisingly little empirical research addressed the effect of performance-based financial incentives on work performance in the literature. In this context, our study makes a contribution to the literature, and we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. Further, due to the scarcity of previous empirical studies that had investigated the links proposed in our study, we are unable to make straight forward comparisons between the findings of our study and findings of previous studies. Therefore, a considerable future research is necessary to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article.

Limitations of the Study and Areas for Future Research

First, the research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. Yet, we went through a tedious process, first, in selecting firms that provide performance-based incentive schemes for technical-level employees; second, in identifying respondents with at least two years of experience with performance-based incentive schemes from the firms. As a consequence, very small number of people qualified to be selected for the sample from a particular firm that meets the above criteria. Therefore, we approached a large number of firms to get an acceptable number of responses. Therefore, we identify our process of selecting respondents for the study as rigorous. We analyzed a limited number of variables of financial incentives, and we used multiple regression for data analysis. Future studies may incorporate other variables such as incentive programme term, quality of goal setting, variations in participation in goal setting, and could use structural equation modeling to investigate interactions among variables. Further, future research studies in different samples that complimented questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data are necessary to validate the links proposed in this study. In such study designs questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Further, although longitudinal research presents a distinctive set of challenges in exploring human related variables such studies may provide a deeper understanding.

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Tables and figure

Figure

FIGURE 1: RESEARCH MODEL

FIGURE 2: MODEL WITH PATH COEFFICIENTS

TABLE 1. SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

	%		%
Age (in years)		Industry sector:	
Between 25-35	64	Telecommunication	58
Between 36-50	31	Healthcare/Biomedical	21
Above 50	5	Automobiles	10
		Power systems/Power generation	11
Gender		Place of work:	
Male	87	Facility based	67
Female	13	Field based	33
Highest level of education		No. of employees (present workplace):	
Advanced level	5	Below 100	4
Diploma	33	100 - 500	57
Degree	62	More than 500	39
Years of experience (present workplace):		No. of technical-level employees (present workplace):	
Less than 5 years	51	Less than 10	59
5 to 10 years	33	11-25	28
More than 10 years	17	26 - 75	11
Total years of experience		More than 75	2
Less than 5 years	32		
5 to 10 years	42		
More than 10 years	26		

TABLE 2. FEATURES OF INCENTIVE SCHEMES

	%
Rewards are based on [†] :	
Meeting or exceeding performance goals	67
Increasing rate of performance (e.g. for each problem solved)	19
Individuals or teams compete with each other	15
Achieving or surpassing a score (eg. KPI score)	18
Profit sharing basis	44
A percentage of monthly salary	24
Incentive scheme type:	
Individual-based	48
Team-based	30
A combination of individual-based and team-based	22
Payout frequency:	
Monthly	43
Quarterly	2
Bi annually	10
Annually	45

[†] do not add up to 100, for each item yes/no question was asked.

TABLE 3. EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION AND INTEGRATION

	Mean	S.D.
Degree of employee participation in setting goals for incentives	2.93	1.02
Degree of integration between incentive scheme and dept/unit goals	3.27	.96

TABLE 4. GOALS OF INCENTIVE SCHEME

	Mean	S.D.
Goals set by the scheme are clear and specific	3.505	0.829
Scheme accurately measure my effort in achieving work goals	3.140	0.928
Goals set by the scheme are challenging but achievable	3.731	0.739
Goals set by the scheme are relevant to my job profile	3.527	1.038
Time period given to achieve the work goals are fair	3.495	0.904
Total mean	3.480	0.598

TABLE 5. REGRESSION RESULTS

	β
Incentive scheme's reward base: meeting or exceeding performance goals	.129
Incentive scheme's reward base: increasing rate of performance	.239
Incentive scheme's reward base: individuals or teams compete with each other	.237
Incentive scheme's reward base: achieving or surpassing a score	.855**
Incentive scheme's reward base: profit sharing basis	.090
Incentive scheme's reward base: a percentage of monthly salary	.571**
Incentive scheme type	.527**
Payout frequency	.381*
Employee participation in setting goals	.431*
Integration with dept/unit goals	.006
Goals of incentive scheme	.893***
Model R ² (Adj.)	.509***

*p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.001